

Research

A Comparative Study on the Adsorption Mechanisms of Natural Montmorillonite for Different Dye Wastewaters

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Abstract: The excessive use of different pigments and dyes in various industries, especially in the textile industry, contributes to environmental pollution. This has had significant consequences. This has also resulted in increased generation of dye within the wastewater streams. This is because some traditional wastewater management and treatment methods are time-consuming and costly. The current study is meant to assess the prospect of natural montmorillonite in treating various dye wastewaters and compare efficiency levels. It will determine the extent of the adsorption of Methylene Blue (MB), Basic Red 18 (BR18) and Basic Blue 41 (BB41) dyes with montmorillonite. In the study, some factors such as the solid-liquid ratio, the pH and the concentration of the dye in the solution as a measure of the adsorption process are discussed. While other parameters, such as the nature of the interactions between montmorillonite and the dyes under study are comprehensively studied. The findings showed that montmorillonite (MMT) had a higher adsorption rate for BR18 while MB and Basic BB41 was low. Parameters studied, which affected the adsorption process, were solution pH, solid to liquid ratio, and contact time. The findings showed that natural montmorillonite is an efficient treatment method for different dye wastewaters. It can be recommended as an environmentally responsible method to address dye pollution. From the outcome of this study, it is possible to have a clear understanding of the efficiency of MMT in the removal of dyes. The data might provide valuable guidelines for enhancing water treatment efficiency.

Keywords: Methylene Blue (MB), Basic Red 18 (BR18), and Basic Blue 41 (BB41), Natural Montmorillonite (MMT), Adsorption, Dye Wastewater.

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1. Introduction

Due to continuous industrial growth, pigment and dye utilization has rapidly increased. The extensive utilization of dyes has resulted in increased generation of colored wastewater which largely contributes to environmental pollution. About 10 to 15% of dyes are lost in waste streams [1]. Most pigments and dyes are toxic and non-biodegradable when discharged within waste streams. Three of the basic dyes in this regard include Methylene Blue (MB), Basic Red 18 (BR18), and Basic Blue 41 (BB41) [2]. The presence of dyes also negatively impacts the water's transparency. Al-Tohamy, Ali [3], says dyes and their by-products are carcinogenic and can negatively impact humans. Additionally, textile effluent can also alter the photosynthesis biological cycle, negatively impacting the food chain and water biodiversity. Dye wastewater is still one of the major sources of pollution of different water bodies in China [4]. Consequently, it is crucial to treat the associated dye effluents prior to their discharge into the environment. Nevertheless, traditional biological procedures are ineffective at removing dyes and other pigments from water bodies. This emphasizes the formulation of alternative effective treatment methods in this regard. As a result, several methods are being investigated for dye removal from an aqueous medium [5]. Different factors such as pH of the solution, temperature, contact time, adsorbent dosage and other associated factors also contribute to Montmorillonite (MMT)'s adsorption performance [6]. Research shows about 60,000 tons of dye waste are discharged every year. However, 80% of these dyes include the azo group which is difficult to treat. In this regard, wastewater discharged by the textile industry is about 900 million tons/year [7]. This has resulted in a global concern regarding the continuous promotion of dye waste. CTAB-MMT has shown effectiveness at treating dye wastewater. Therefore, one of the most commonly used natural adsorbents is MMT. It is represented as a clay mineral with a negative charge permanently. This is because of the isomorphous substitution of "Mg²⁺ for Al³⁺" within an octahedral layer and "Al³⁺ for Si⁴⁺" within a tetrahedral layer [8]. To balance this negative charge, different exchangeable cations are also present within the lattice structure. These ions include Na⁺, Ca²⁺ and others within the lattice structure. This helps ensure the efficient performance of the associated adsorbent, by adsorbing various cationic contaminants, using ion exchange. Therefore, the current study has also highlighted different factors which contribute to MMT's ability as an adsorbent. In this study, we focus on three prominent dyes that are considered to be major contributors to wastewater pollution. These include MB, BR18, and BB41 dyes. This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of MMT as an adsorbent for those dyes. Thus, it examines different factors influencing dye adsorption on MMT. This includes the underlying mechanisms that govern MMT interactions with various dyes. Additionally, MMT's efficiency as a vital solution for dye wastewater treatment has also been investigated.

2. Methodology

MMT has been used because of its large surface area and a high cation exchange capacity (CEC) to adsorb pollutants [9]. Specifically, two types of MMTs were used: Two types of organoclays were prepared namely calcium montmorillonite (Ca-Mont) and titanium modified montmorillonite (Ti-Mont). The University of Missouri–Columbia Source Clay Minerals Repository (SAz-1) provided all this data [10]. This repository is in Columbia, Missouri. Ca-Mont's 120 meq/100 g cation exchange capacity (CEC) suggests it could be used effectively in cation exchange operations. The CEC of Ca-Mont is 120 meq/100g, which indicates the high capability of the material for spreading cations and adsorption. The preparation of Ti-Mont involved chemical modification through an ion-exchange process in which calcium ions on the clay surface were replaced by titanium ions using one normal TiCl₄ solution. This led to the saturation of the montmorillonite with titanium; in order to determine the titanium content within the samples, the samples were freeze-dried and their titanium content quantified using ICP-AES. This modification was done to increase the adsorption capacity

of the clay for certain applications since Ti-Mont possesses more surface area and thus more of interaction with the different pollutants [11]. The adsorption tests involved the removal of synthetic dyes, MB; BR18; and BB41, from aqueous solutions flexible [12]. These dyes are utilized commonly in textile industries and are grouped as reactive dyes due to their ability to withstand water.

2.1. Experimental procedure

The experimental procedures involved the addition of 0.1 g of MMT into 100 mL of dye solution. The adsorption experiment was performed at 25°C and the initial pH of the solution was adjusted to 3 with either NaOH or HCl to enhance the adsorption efficiency of the MMT for basic dyes. The concentration of dye was determined at intervals of 5 to 60 minutes to determine the time that is required for adsorption to reach a steady state and was determined to be 30 minutes. The absorbance values were read at 655 nm for MB and BR18, and at 555 nm for BB41. In order to find the adsorption capacity, the formula $Q = V \times \Delta C / m$ was used where V is the volume of solution, ΔC is change of concentration of dye and m is mass of the adsorbent. This facilitated a direct comparison of the efficiency of dye removal by both Ca-Mont and Ti-Mont. Further characterization of the MMT samples was done by X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis to check for any change in the crystalline structure after adsorption. Porosity was further analyzed by nitrogen adsorption isotherms at 77K to determine the BET surface area, pore size distribution, and total pore volume. These parameters gave information on the changes in the textural features of MMT before and after dye adsorption. The results also indicated that the adsorption behavior of MMT depended on solid-to-liquid ratio, pH and initial dye concentration. Besides, acidic solution with pH of 3 was most suitable for the adsorption of these basic dyes because the electrostatic attraction between the negatively charged surface of the clay and the positively charged dye ions was greatly boosted. Adsorption isotherm plots were made to study the relationship between the adsorption capacity and dye concentration.

2.2. Data analysis

The adsorption data were obtained to adsorption studies, where the adsorption capacity (Q) was determined by dividing the product $V \times \Delta C$ by m . Dye concentration changes at certain wavelengths (655 nm for MB and BR18, 555 nm for BB41) were determined using UV-visible spectrophotometry. Isotherm studies were carried out to judge the extent of interaction between MMT and dye molecules, and the data thus obtained complied with the isotherm Langmuir model, which asserts that a monolayer was formed. XRD and BET analyses were employed to determine the effects on the crystalline structure and surface area of the dye adsorbed MMT to assess its efficacy in the removal of dye pollutants from aqueous solutions.

3. Results and Discussion

This study focuses on analysing the adsorption of montmorillonite (MMT) for Methylene Blue (MB), Basic Red 18 (BR18), and Basic Blue 41 (BB41). The study also includes characterization, sample identification, and adsorption studies using XRD analysis to determine the ability of MMT as a natural adsorbent in wastewater treatment. Implications for the nanostructure of the adsorbents, rate of adsorption and the effect of parameters including pH, slurry solid/liquid ratio and contact time were also passed on.

3.1. XRD Results

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis is shown to be of great significance when describing the crystallography of the adsorbent materials. In this study, the XRD of MMT, HT, and attapulgite samples carefully examined the structural stability and suitability of dye adsorption.

Fig 3.1. XRD results of MMT

Montmorillonite (MMT), Sharp peaks in the XRD graphs indicated that it is crystalline in nature at different angles. The highest frequency was recorded above 60 with a frequency density of 300, other high frequency was found to be 35 with a frequency density of 110 and 20 with frequency density of 100. Other minor peaks were observed at 18 degrees and 30 degrees indicating that there are in fact layered structures of MMT.

Fig 3.2. XRD results of HT

Halloysite (HT), HT exhibited the highest intensity of over 60 degrees with 300 while other maximal intensity of was revealed at 55 degrees with 210 reduces, 35 degrees with 110 reduces, and 20 degrees with 100 reduces. Other minor intensity maxima were observed at angles greater than 10 degrees clearly showing the sample to have highly crystalline nature.

Fig 3.3. XRD results of attapulgite

Attapulgite, conversely, the optimal coefficients of attapulgite were recognized at 25 degrees, 20 degrees, and 35 degrees. These results highlight its unique features: higher crystallinity, which are crucial for estimating the adsorption capacity. This XRD investigation finally confirms that all the adsorbents developed in this work possess crystalline structures for dye adsorption.

3.2. Sample Differentiation

The montmorillonite as an adsorbent for MB, BR18, and BB41 was monitored using factors such as the solid to liquid ratio and change in the ph. The kinetic behavior of MB adsorption was analyzed across different solid-to-liquid ratios: 0.5 g/L, 1.0 g/L, and 1.5 g/L.

Fig 3.4. Adsorption of MB with distinct different solid-to-liquid ratios

It was observed that the adsorption of MB was affected by solid-to-liquid ratios of the prepared nanocomposites. The highest adsorption was achieved at concentration of 0.5 g/L of dye which indicates that low solid/liquid ratio favors dye adsorption. The lowest adsorption has been obtained at the maximum used concentration 1.5 g/L, with constant decrease in the concentration until the absolute minimum after 60 min of the time. Effect of pH the study revealed that the pH of the solution significantly affects the amount of dye adsorbed.

Fig 3.5. Adsorption of MB with distinct pH

This study compared MB adsorption at different pH; 3, 5 and 10. The highest adsorption was obtained at pH=3 and the lowest at pH=10. This indicates that acidic environment favors the formation of MB-montmorillonite complex through charge density mechanism perhaps because of increased surface protonation of the adsorbent.

3.3. Adsorption Experiments

Four-point adsorption experiments were to study the state of equilibrium for MB, BR18, and BB41 with a constant dose of 0.5g/L montmorillonite clay.

Fig 3.6. 0.5g montmorillonite adsorption of 500 mg/L MB adsorption equilibrium diagram

At the concentration of 500 mg/L the adsorption rate was considerably higher than that in the case with 50 mg/L of Cu(II) ions; however, it was still rather low, and the maximal degree of adsorption achieved did not exceed 0.7% after 240 minutes. Even after longer contact periods, the percentage removal of MB was very low, this suggests that montmorillonite may not be the best adsorbent for this specific dye.

Fig 3.7. Adsorption equilibrium diagram of 0.5g montmorillonite adsorption of 500 mg/L BR18

BR18 had a higher adsorption rate than MB in the study carried out here. Of BR18, 0.35% was adsorbed in the first 5 minutes, and this increased to 0.75% after 200 minutes. This evidence stronger interaction of BR18 with montmorillonite, which, in turn, points to this reagent as more preferable for adsorption processes with the help of this material.

Fig 3.8. Adsorption equilibrium diagram of 0.5g montmorillonite adsorption of 500 mg/L BB41

As for BB41, the adsorption efficiency was smallest of the three dyes, at 0.3% within the first 50 minutes, increasing maximally to 0.45% at 250 minutes. This means that perhaps BB41 needs other adsorbents or some changes to montmorillonite to enhance its adsorption coefficients. The work also identified the possibility of using other natural adsorbents like halloysite and attapulgite in the removal of the selected dyes from the aqueous solution.

Fig 3.9. Halloysite adsorbs different concentrations of MB

The halloysite achieved fluctuated adsorption rates in relation to increased dye concentration but was less efficient than montmorillonite. This implies that the halloysite has some extent of ability of removing dyes, but they are inferior to that of montmorillonite when unaltered.

Fig 3.10. Attapulgite adsorbs different concentrations of MB

The results indicated that while attapulgite also has some adsorption performance on dyes, the adsorption capacity was different for each dye. More work is required to understand how best to apply and exploit it, and how it might be applied with other adsorbents if at all. Several critical factors were identified as influencing the adsorption process, lengthy contact time mostly results in high adsorption rates of all dyes tested on the material. From these data, it is inferred that higher initial concentrations of the dyes raise the overall adsorption capacity in case montmorillonite is used as the adsorbent. Lower solid-to-liquid ratios increase dye uptake rates for all dyes tested but particularly for the BR18. Consequently, the study demonstrates that montmorillonite can reveal great promise in the removal of basic dyes from wastewaters notably Basic Red 18. However, the adsorption efficiency value for the Methylene Blue and Basic Blue 41 remains low, therefore, for these dyes the potential for montmorillonite modification or its joint use with other materials may be considered. The effects of parameters such as solid-liquid ratios, pH, and contact time, which affect the adsorption process can be manipulated in order to enhance the amount of dye removed within the system. Future studies should target the enhancement of the adsorption capacity of montmorillonite through derivatization or through

used in conjunction with another natural adsorbent such as halloysite and attapulgite. They could improve the performance of the material in practice, and provide a more effective, environmentally friendly and relatively inexpensive method for wastewater treatment.

Fig 3.11 Halloysite adsorbs different concentrations of BB18

This figure provides the adsorption profile of BB18 at different ratios namely 100 mg/L, 300 mg/L and 500 mg/L. The graph represents the relation between the ratio of dye concentration at the time of adsorption, C_t and initial concentration C_0 . Based on the solid-to-liquid ratio of 100 mg/L, the highest percentage adsorption of BB18 was discovered to be the lowest. The adsorption rate was highly elevated until 45 minutes but remained constant after 60 minutes. However, at a solid to liquid ratio of 500 mg/L, the BB18 show its maximum adsorption capacity. Here, the adsorption rate declined at 20 min and then increased gradually further proving that time is a very important factor that affects dye adsorption rates.

Fig 3.12 Halloysite adsorbs different concentrations of BB41

The adsorption behavior of BB41 at different solids/liquid ratio of 100 mg/L, 300 mg/L and 500 mg/L is shown in this figure, it is also clear that the mass ratio of solid to liquid was 100 mg/L, then the adsorption extent of BB41 was the

least. As with BB41 adsorption, there was a steep drop initially within the first 20 minutes, after which the rate of decrease was slower. The maximum adsorption requires a ratio of solid to liquid of 500 mg/l of BB41. The trends established shows that as the concentration increases then more dye uptake occurs.

Fig 3.13 Adsorption of BB18 by different solid liquid

This figure presents the amount of C_t/C_0 ratio of BB18 at different concentrations over time. It shows that aim this study, at a concentration of 2.0 g/L, C_t/C_0 of BB18 is the highest and therefore adsorption is also at its peak. The slope of each concentration level offers information concerning the rate of adsorption; high slopes relate to fast adsorption of the first fifteen minutes and low slope in the subsequent time period.

Fig 3.14 Different solid-liquid adsorption of halloysite BB41

The figure demonstrates the absorption of BB41 sample for 8 hours having different ratios of solid and liquid. The x-axis gives time and the y-axis gives the C_t/C_0 value. The graph also shows that at a constant BB41 concentration, attapulgit has a greater adsorption capacity when the S/L ratios is low. The divergence of the lines proved the effect of different solid to liquid ratios toward adsorption capacity.

Fig 3.15. 0.5g/L montmorillonite adsorbs different concentrations of methylene blue (MB)

This figure is a comparative experiment in which montmorillonite (0.5 g/L) adsorbs various concentrations of methylene blue. The graph depicts how montmorillonite adsorbs varying amounts of methylene blue across three concentrations: Concentrations were 100 mg/L, 300 mg/L, and 500 mg/L. On the y axis is the amount adsorbed and on the x axis is concentration levels. The orange bar refers to absorption at the concentration of 500 mg/L, green at 300 mg/L and purple absorption at 100 mg/L. The data here indicate that at higher concentrations, greater capacity for absorption is accomplished where signs of saturation are revealed by bar height.

Fig 3.16. 0.5g/L montmorillonite adsorbs different concentrations of basic red 18

The following figure shows montmorillonite absorption for basic red 18 in relation to the concentration. This is a graph which like figure 4.15 it illustrates how increasing concentrations, or the absorption of BR18 by montmorillonite at 0.5 g/L. The green color represents the absorption of samples with 500 mg/L while the purple represents that of samples at 300 mg/L and blue at 100 mg/L. The ratios observed follow similar patterns as those seen with MB, confirming that higher concentrations are associated with elevated absorption rates until those levels have been reached.

Fig 3.17. 0.5g/L montmorillonite adsorbs different concentrations of basic blue 41 (BB41)

The following figure shows the montmorillonite adsorption affinity for basic blue 41 at various concentrations. Once more, higher concentrations proved to have a direct link with permissible absorption rates until the RLH reaches its limit.

Fig 3.18. Isotherm adsorption models of attapulgite for different dyes at constant temperature.

These graphs analyze the absorption of Methylene Blue (MB) using two models; the Langmuir and Freundlich models. According to the Langmuir model, intensively adsorbed dye molecules are brought onto definite homogeneous sites within attapulgite, where a single site can only accommodate one dye molecule at a time, yielding monolayer coverage. On the other hand, the Freundlich model considers the heterogeneity of the surfaces permitting multilayer adsorption values. Isotherm Models for BB41 Figures (c) and (d): These graphs show how the two isotherm models represent the

data that was generated from BB41 experiment. Retention parameters values indicating high correlation with dye concentration confirm both monolayer and multilayer mechanisms in attapulgite. Isotherm Models for BB18 Figures (e) and (f): These exact same trends are observed in these graphs linked to BB18 interaction with attapulgite using both isotherm model and linear methods. Multiple mechanisms of dye adsorption on attapulgite surface can be confirmed by both models that provided high r^2 values.

This research found out that, indeed, halloysite and attapulgite are promising adsorbents for numerous dyes at various circumstances. Higher solid-liquid ratio increases the dye uptake as time affects the rate of the adsorption process. The analysis for both Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms is important in understanding how these dyes react with clay minerals at molecular level as a way of effective purification of water using natural resources such as clay.

Montmorillonite (MMT) is another useful adsorbent in treating dye wastewater since it has a huge surface area and embraces high central charge density. These suggest that MMT is a cheap and eco-friendly adsorbent for addressing industrial dye waste problems. The study shows how adsorption capacity depends on factors such as contact time and pH that determine the optimum effectiveness of the MMT in adsorbing such as Methylene Blue (MB), Basic Blue 41 (BB41), and Basic Red 18 (BR18). It is quite clear that contact time plays a crucial role especially regarding the adsorption capability. First, the dye adsorption process increases sharply because the active sites of MMT are easily available, but gradually reduces as these areas get occupied [13]. Dye ionization and surface charge are influenced by pH values directly. For instance, under increased pH level, BB41 has the ability to adsorb more since the electrostatic attraction between the dye and the nanomaterial becomes stronger, which is not the same case with BR18 as it is an acidic dye and hence has better affinity to more acidic condition [14]. It is clear that the adsorption of MMT and other adsorbents such as halloysite and attapulgite may vary with some conditions. From the above data it is clear that the quantity of MMT affects the MB adsorption capacity, stressing the importance of the solid-liquid ratio in the dye efficiency. Maximum adsorption capacity of MB is attained at near neutral pH levels due reduced charged attractions, although the relatively low adsorption abilities of both halloysite and attapulgite at high dye concentration indicate surface saturation of the available dye molecules [15]. Among them, BR18 attributed the highest adsorption on MMT which is based on the chemistry between the adsorbent and dye. On the other hand, MB was shown to have the highest adsorption, while BB41 had the least. These outcomes show that more knowledge of the chemical form and its involvement with the current MMT systems are required to improve wastewater treatment systems [16]. Comparative analysis with MB, dye removal efficiency decreases at higher dye concentration proving that MMT has reached saturation as observed with other adsorbents. Major factors that influence the effectiveness of an adsorbent include the solid-liquid ratios, an MMT pre-treatment step results in an increase in the quantity of dye adsorbed. The experiments also support the pH values will enhance most of the adsorption since the adsorbent has some ionic properties with the dyes. Nevertheless, at these higher dye concentrations, MMT, attapulgite and halloysite seems to reach its saturation level, and it will be necessary to determine the optimum dosage of these adsorbents. The molecular nature of adsorption was explained using isotherm models of Langmuir and Freundlich; that indicated monolayer and multilayer mechanism affecting the dye-MMT interactions [17]. Based on these results, there is considerable scope for the synthesis of inexpensive and effective water treatment technologies employing natural clays.

4. Conclusion

This paper investigated the effectiveness of MMT along with attapulgite and Halloysite, as adsorbents in the dye wastewater treatment, by emphasizing on MB, BR18, and BB41. The study was based on experiments of adsorption to evaluate the adsorbent's effectiveness across various conditions like solid-liquid ratios, dye concentrations, and pH levels. The findings suggested that the capacity of adsorption of MMT rises when there is a rise in the adsorbents' quantity, which shows that there is a potential solid-liquid ratio which results in enhancement of the procedure of adsorption which helps in dye removal at the maximum level. In addition to that, the impact of pH on the efficiency of adsorption

was under observation during the experiment, with neutral condition of pH, helping in better removal of dye, showing that there is a strong impact of MMT's ionic nature and the molecules of dye at time of their interaction and the further removal of dye. The impact of pH on the efficiency of adsorption was also observed, with a neutral condition of pH helping in better removal of dye, highlighting the influence of MMT ionic nature and the molecules of dye on their interaction and the further efficacy of adsorption. To conclude, this paper focuses on the significance of attapulgite, montmorillonite, and halloysite as effective adsorbents for the treatment of wastewater, with potential implications for health of public and conservation of environment waste. The insights gain from the examination makes the way for future studies by focusing on development of adsorption base treatment solutions providing contribution towards the broader goal of environmental protection and sustainable water management.

This study mostly affirms that natural clay minerals such as montmorillonite, halloysite and attapulgite possess the ability to adsorb synthetic dyes from wastewaters by providing environmentally friendly option as compared to chemically charged treatments. It elucidates the possibilities for efficient and inexpensive wastewater treatment methods, which can promote industrial developments. The study also resolves multiple interdisciplinary areas and contributes to the further development of adsorption technology as well as to international initiatives for sustainable resource use and environmental policy. This experimental study shows how natural montmorillonite (MMT) is useful in the adsorption of three dye wastes, MB, BR18, and BB41 from wastewater though it has some limitations such as its concentration is only in China, and it did not show how it interacts with other chemicals used in dyeing industries. Future studies should be focused on investigation in other areas, other dyeing agents, and, especially, experimental studies should encompass wider range of conditions to improve practical usability of MMT in wastewater treatment technologies.

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